

ISic3435

I.Sicily inscription 3435

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building (?)

Material

stone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

A 'vignaletto' below the road that leads into Mineo from the west
through the 'Udienza' gate, found 1813

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336160

1. [— — Αἰ] | σχρίωνα καὶ Νυ | μφόδωρο[ν] | Βομβυλίνου.
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644914

EDCS 70900815

PHI 336160

Bibliography

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